

Synthesis, characterization, thermal studies and molecular modeling of embelinsemicarbazone and its metal complexes

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Abstract : Embelinsemicarbazone (H₃ESC) synthesized by condensing embelin with semicarbazide hydrochloride, has been characterized by UV, IR and ¹H NMR spectra. The chelates of H₃ESC with metals ions such as Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, VO^{II}, UO₂^{II} and MoO₂^{II} were prepared. Physico-chemical and spectral analyses of the complexes show that the ligand acts as monovalent tridentate. The chelates of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} are four coordinated with square planar geometry and VO^{II} square pyramidal. The complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, UO₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} are found to be six coordinated with distorted octahedral geometry. Thermal analysis of [Zn(H₂ESC)₂] showed a three stage decomposition pattern. Computer models of the ligand and its MoO₂^{II} complex were constructed using interactive software Hyperchem 5.01 Release.

Keywords : Embelin, semicarbazone, molecular modeling.

The chelating properties of Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy aldehydes and ketones display manifold application in medicine, industry and agriculture¹. Embelin is one such 2-hydroxyketone which can form Schiff bases with semicarbazide and thio-semicarbazide. Semicarbazones have attracted special attention as antilepral, antitubercular, antiviral, antimalarial, anticancer and antibacterial drugs. Metal semicarbazones are reported to be active against small pox, viral diseases and certain kinds of tumours². In continuation of our work on the complexes of embelin and its derivatives, the synthesis, characterization, molecular modeling and thermal studies of embelinsemicarbazone (H₃ESC) and its metal chelates are presented³.

Results and discussion

H₃ESC is a yellow crystalline solid with m.p. 185 °C. The CHN analysis and molecular mass determination by cryoscopy, using biphenyl as solvent, revealed that H₃ESC is a monosemicarbazone. IR spectrum of H₃ESC gives bands at 3480 and 3410 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretches of NH₂ group. A broad band is observed at 3300 cm⁻¹ is due to the stretching frequency of intramolecularly hy-

drogen bonded OH group. The band observed at 3181 cm⁻¹ is due to NH stretching frequency. Strong bands in H₃ESC observed at 1714 and 1690 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the stretching of the carbonyl and bending of the N-H bond respectively, of the amide⁴. The quinonoid carbonyl and the azomethine stretching frequencies are observed at 1625 and 1570 cm⁻¹ respectively in H₃ESC. The ¹H NMR spectral data of H₃ESC, in CDCl₃ gives three-proton triplet at δ 0.9 corresponding to the methyl group at the end of the side chain (C-17). The methylene proton multiplets corresponding to eighteen protons (C-8 to C-16) are observed at δ 1.3. A triplet of two protons at δ 2.35 corresponds to the methylene group attached to the ring (C-7). A doublet peak is observed at δ 2.2 corresponding to the NH₂ protons and a singlet peak at δ 4.4 can be attributed to the NH proton which shows the presence of keto-enol tautomerism in the semicarbazone moiety of the ligand. A singlet at δ 5.4 for one proton in the ligand obtained is due to the ring proton at C-6. A very sharp singlet peak at δ 7.25 corresponding to two protons is observed which can be attributed to the protons of the two OH groups in the ligand.

The tautomerisation of 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthaquinones into their 4-hydroxy-1,2-naphthaquinone form in solu-

tion during complexation with metals has been reported⁵. This type of 1,3-tautomerism is also reported for the thiosemicarbazone of phthiocol (4-hydroxy-3-methyl-1,2-naphthoquinone-1-thiosemicarbazone) and confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction study of the above compound⁶. From the IR and NMR spectral data of H₃ESC which is also an orthofunctionalized paraquinone derivative, it can be suggested that it also exhibits 1,3 tautomerism. There is a tautomerisation of C-2 hydroxyl group into a quinonoidal carbonyl at C-4 position in the embelin ring. This tautomeric form is stabilized by the intramolecular hydrogen bond between semicarbazone nitrogen and quinonoidal oxygen⁷.

Thus the structure of H₃ESC is given below :

Embelinsemicarbazone (H₃ESC)

Complexes of embelinsemicarbazone (H₃ESC) :

All the complexes of H₃ESC synthesized are coloured, stable and soluble in organic solvents such as methanol and chloroform. From the analytical data as in Table 1, the metal to ligand ratio of complexes was found to be 1 : 2 in the case of all the complexes except those of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}. In Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes the metal to ligand ratio is found to be 1 : 1. The molar conductance values measured in solvents such as nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol are very low showing that all the complexes behave as non electrolytes except those of Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} in which they behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes⁸.

Comparison of the infrared spectral data of the metal complexes with H₃ESC indicates the disappearance of the NH stretching band at 3180 cm⁻¹ and the ν_{C=O} of amide observed at 1714 cm⁻¹ in the ligand during complex formation and new bands appear above 1600 cm⁻¹ and around 1380 cm⁻¹⁹. The presence of bands around 1600 and 1380 cm⁻¹ in the complexes is due to ν_{N=C} and ν_{C-O} respectively of NCO⁻ group, which shows the removal of a hydrazinic proton via enolisation and subsequent participation of enolic oxygen in coordination^{10,11}.

The azomethine stretch (ν_{C=N}) observed at 1571 cm⁻¹ for the ligand is shifted to lower energy side around 1510 cm⁻¹ in complexes suggesting the coordination through nitrogen of the azomethine group¹²⁻¹⁴. A band at 945 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{N-N} undergoes a positive shift to around 970 cm⁻¹ showing the bonding through one hydrazinic nitrogen¹⁵.

The hydroxyl groups of embelin ring absorbing at a frequency of around 3303 cm⁻¹ in the ligand remain unaltered showing their non-participation in chelation. But the carbonyl group of the ring absorbing at 1624 cm⁻¹ in the ligand suffers a shift to lower energy around 1580 cm⁻¹ in the complexes showing its participation in complex formation. Thus the ligand acts as a monovalent tridentate ONO donor, in the form (H₂ESC)⁻. The presence of nonligand bands between 600-550 and 500-550 cm⁻¹ respectively in complexes are due to M-N and M-O stretch^{16,17}. M-Cl stretch is observed in the far IR region of around 300-350 cm⁻¹ in complexes showing the presence of the chloride in complexes¹⁸. Nitrate complexes give characteristic medium intensity bands at 1480 and 1310 cm⁻¹ (ν₄ and ν₁) with a separation of about 170 cm⁻¹ due to monodentately coordinated nitrate ion. They also give combination bands (ν₁ + ν₄) at 1740 and 1720 cm⁻¹ with separation of 20 cm⁻¹ showing their monodentate behaviour¹⁶. In case of perchlorate complexes four bands are observed around 1140, 1070, 650 and 610 cm⁻¹ assignable respectively to ν₃, ν₁, ν₄ and ν₅ vibration modes of unidentately coordinated perchlorate group^{19,20}.

¹H NMR spectrum of the MoO₂^{II} complex shows the absence of the peak at δ 4.4 due to the NH proton in the ligand indicating the complexation through nitrogen via deprotonation.

All the metal complexes are paramagnetic except Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, UO₂^{II} and MoO₂^{II} complexes which are diamagnetic. In addition to the charge transfer transition exhibited by all the complexes, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} give bands characteristic of square planar geometry. VO^{II} complex gives bands due to square pyramidal geometry. The complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} give absorptions characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry.

ESR spectrum of VO^{II} complex (Fig. 1) gives a hyperfine split of 8 lines each in parallel and perpendicular components. Spin-Hamiltonian parameter A_{||} and A_⊥ are calculated as 118.75 and 62.5 G respectively. g_{||} and g_⊥ are calculated respectively as 1.96 and 2.00 G. These values are in agreement with those observed for square

pyramidal geometry²¹. The trend $g_{||} < g_{\perp} < g_e$ (free ion) is observed for the complex showing that the unpaired electron is in d_{xy} orbital of VO^{II} ion²². In the ESR spectrum of Cu^{II} complex hyperfine splitting is seen in the parallel component with partial overlapping but not in the perpendicular component. $A_{||}$ is calculated as 200 G and A_{\perp} as 'zero'. $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} are found to be 2.427 and 2.045 G respectively. The trend $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (free ion) is observed for the complex showing that the unpaired electron is in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of Cu^{II} ion and the spectrum obtained is characteristic of axial symmetry²³.

Structure of $[M(H_2ESC)X]$
 $M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, UO_2^{II}, VO^{II}, MoO_2^{II}$;
 $X = Cl^-, NO_3^-$

Structure of $[M(H_2ESC)_2]$
 $M = Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}$

Computer modeling :

Molecular modeling of H_3ESC and the complex $[MoO_2(H_2ESC)Cl]$ are made by Hyperchem 5.01 Professional release^{24,25}. Low strained configurations of the ligand and the complex obtained from the computer are as given in Figs. 2 and 3.

Thermal decomposition studies :

Thermogram of $[Zn(H_2ESC)_2]$ shows a three stages

decomposition pattern and the temperature ranges between 150–300, 310–500 and 505–780 °C. The exotherms give mass losses corresponding to the oxidative degradation of the semicarbazone and embelin moieties respectively, of the ligand. Final residue corresponds to ZnO . Other complexes of the ligand also follow the same decomposition pattern.

Evaluation of thermodynamic and kinetic parameters :

The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters of the metal complex have been evaluated for each of the decomposition stages using Coats-Redfern equation^{26,27}. For each of the well defined decomposition stage, the order parameter 'n', energy of activation E , pre-exponential factor A and entropy of activation ΔS^* have been calculated. The activation energy for the last stage is found to be higher than those of other earlier stages of thermal decomposition. The negative values observed of ΔS^* show that the activated states are more ordered than the respective reactants in all the stages of decomposition.

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammetric studies show that the ligand H_3ESC and its Cu^{II} and VO^{II} complexes in DMF exhibit only cathodic potentials²⁸. They do not show any observable oxidation wave upon the reverse scan of the cyclic voltammogram and thus exhibit irreversible redox behaviour²⁹. The ligand does not show redox activity at the potential where copper and vanadium reductions are observed. Electrochemical studies of $Cu^{II,I}$ and $VO^{II,I}$ systems are limited by the fact that the two electron reductions of both the systems are more favorable than the one electron reduction.

Experimental

All the reagents used for the isolation of embelin and synthesis of H_3ESC and its complexes are of A.R. grade.

Embelin was isolated from the air dried, powdered berries of *Embelia ribes*. The powdered berries were extracted with hexane using a Soxhlet apparatus. The extract was cooled and filtered to orange coloured residue. This was recrystallised from methanol as orange plates with melting point 144 °C. Purity was tested by TLC.

Synthesis of H_3ESC :

1 g of semicarbazide hydrochloride and 1 g sodium acetate was dissolved in 1 : 1 ethanol (25 ml). A hot solution of 3 g embelin was added to the above clear solution and kept on a water bath for 30 min when yellow crystalline precipitate of semicarbazone separated out. This was cooled, suction filtered, washed well with hot

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes of H₃ESC

Complex	%Composition (Calcd.)			Electrolytic nature	Magnetic moment (B.M.)	Electronic spectra (cm ⁻¹)
	N	Cl	Metal			
[Cu(H ₂ ESC)(NO ₃)] (Brown)	11.5 (11.8)	-	12.8 (13.3)	Non electrolyte	1.82	12500 - ² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g} 21200 - ² B _{1g} → ² E _g
[Cu(H ₂ ESC)Cl] (Brown)	-	7.3 (7.46)	14.3 (14.1)			25700 - charge transfer (ct)
[Ni(H ₂ ESC)(NO ₃)] (Brown)	11.3 (11.89)	-	12.4 (12.5)	Non electrolyte	Diamagnetic	12300 - ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _g 18500 - ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{2g}
[Ni(H ₂ ESC)Cl] (Brown)	-	7.8 (7.9)	12.2 (13.2)			22000 - ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g} 27500 - ct
[Co(H ₂ ESC) ₂] (Brown)	10.9 (11.1)	-	8.7 (7.8)	Non electrolyte	5.3	9500 - ⁴ T _{1g(F)}} → ⁴ T _{2g(F)}} 18200 - ⁴ T _{1g(F)}} → ⁴ A _{2g(F)}} 21200 - ⁴ T _{1g(F)}} → ⁴ T _{1g(P)}}
[Mn(H ₂ ESC) ₂] (Brown)	10.8 (11.12)	-	7.2 (7.28)	Non electrolyte	5.89	19830 - ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} 23500 - ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ E _g
[Zn(H ₂ ESC) ₂] (Brown)	10.8 (10.97)	-	8.3 (8.54)	Non electrolyte	Diamagnetic	Charge transfer
[Fe(H ₂ ESC) ₂]Cl (Black)	10.4 (10.6)	4.3 (4.5)	6.2 (7.06)	1 : 1	5.8	17200 - ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} 21500 - ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
[Fe(H ₂ ESC) ₂]ClO ₄ (Black)	-	4.0 (4.2)	6.1 (6.53)	1 : 1		26500 - ct
[Cr(H ₂ ESC) ₂]Cl (Black)	10.5 (10.7)	4.3 (4.5)	6.3 (6.6)	1 : 1	3.8	18400 - ⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g} 27000 - charge transfer
[Cr(H ₂ ESC) ₂]ClO ₄ (Black)	-	3.9 (4.2)	5.9 (6.11)	1 : 1		
[VO ₂ (H ₂ ESC)Cl] (9.2)	9.1 (9.2)	7.6 (7.8)	11.3 (11.2)	Non electrolyte	1.7	23200 - charge transfer 17200 - ⁶ d _{xy} → d _{x²-y²} 13070 - d _{xy} → d _{yz} , d _{zx}
[UO ₂ (H ₂ ESC)Cl] (6.4)	6.2 (6.4)	5.2 (5.2)	36.1 (36.3)	Non electrolyte	Diamagnetic	25316 - ct (lig → met) 20833 - ct ¹ Σ _g ⁺ → ³ Π _u
[MoO ₂ (H ₂ ESC)Cl] (8.2)	8.0 (8.2)	7.0 (6.9)	18.4 (18.6)	Non electrolyte	Diamagnetic	25315 - charge transfer

water and finally with aqueous ethanol, dried and recrystallised from methanol.

All the complexes were synthesized by mixing hot ethanolic solution (0.05 M) of embelinsemicarbazone and the respective metal salt solution (0.06 M) in aqueous ethanol and refluxing them over a water bath for about 3 h. Afterwards it was concentrated, cooled and the solid separated was filtered, washed well with hot water and finally with aqueous ethanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ in vacuum.

The elemental analysis was carried out by micro analytical method on Hewlett-Packard CHN-185 analyzer at

CDRI, Lucknow. Electrical conductance measurements of the complexes for 10⁻³ M solutions in acetonitrile, nitrobenzene and methanol were carried out at 301 ± 2 K using a Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter type-303. Magnetic moments were calculated from magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes measured by Gouy method using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as the calibrant. Electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded using Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer in methanol in the range of 200–900 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Infra red spectra were recorded using KBr discs using Perkin-Elmer 1650 FTIR spectrophotometer between 4000–200

Fig. 1. ESR spectrum of [VO(H₂ESC)Cl]

nm Proton NMR spectra of the compound was recorded in CDCl₃ using JEOL-EX90 FT NMR spectrometer. Electron spin resonance spectra of the complexes of Cu^{II} and VO^{II} were recorded in the solid state at room temperature using DPPH as the standard in a Varian E-4 X-band EPR spectrometer. The TG and DTG analyses of the complex was carried out using a DuPont 2000 Thermal Analyzer system, in conjunction with a 951 Thermogravimetric Analyzer with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and a sample size of 2–3 mg in an atmosphere of nitrogen using a platinum crucible. Cyclic voltammetric studies were done on a CV 50W system using a three electrode system with glassy carbon as the working electrode, Pt as the auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl as the working electrode. Tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate was used as the supporting electrode. Scanning was done

Fig. 2. Molecular model of H₂ESC

Fig. 3. Molecular model of [MoO₂(H₂ESC)Cl]

at the rate of 100 mV/s in the range of +2000 mV to -2000 mV

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